

TOWARDS IMPROVING LEGISLATION ON COMBATING MASS DISORDERS

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ABSTRACT: This article analyzes the essence of amendments and additions made to the legislation on combating mass disorders, important conceptual approaches to regulating the fight against mass disorders, and the experience of some developed countries in this regard.

Keywords: public safety, mass disorders, incitement, weapons of mass destruction, explosives.

Mass disorders pose a real threat to public safety, public order, the foundations of the constitutional system, and state security. In this regard, there is an objective need for timely theoretical and scientific-practical research to prevent them. Such studies serve as a basis for the prompt adoption of appropriate measures to protect life, health, and property, as well as to restore the normal functioning of infrastructure and life support facilities.

Mass disorders are a widespread phenomenon, encompassing a combination of various socially dangerous actions, primarily of a violent nature, carried out mainly by large groups. These actions threaten the foundations of public safety and are capable of destabilizing the activities of government bodies, institutions, and other organizations, as well as significantly disrupting public order in important areas. The high level of social danger and the wide scale of mass riots necessitate the development and constant improvement of measures to combat these criminal phenomena, primarily preventive measures, taking into account the modern criminal-legal and criminological characteristics of such criminal encroachments.

In modern conditions, the prevention of mass riots is further complicated by the fact that their organization, facilitation, and direct implementation are often associated with the criminal activities of extremist and terrorist groups and organizations, primarily through the dissemination of relevant ideology and the active use of the extensive capabilities of the Internet and other information and communication technologies.[1]

Currently, Article 244 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan contains provisions related to mass riots. [2] Specifically, publicly inciting mass riots and violence against citizens is punishable by a fine ranging from one hundred to three hundred times the basic calculation amount, or correctional labor for up to two years, or restriction of liberty from three to five years, or imprisonment from three to five years. If the same actions are committed by a group of persons through prior conspiracy or using mass media, telecommunications networks, the Internet, as well as printed or other methods of text reproduction, they are punishable by a fine ranging from three hundred to four hundred times the basic calculation amount, or correctional labor from two to three years, or imprisonment from five to ten years.

In accordance with Law No. LRU-1051 of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 27, 2025, Article 244 of the Criminal Code was supplemented with parts three, four, and five. [3] It establishes liability for undergoing training with the purpose of committing mass riots, including learning to handle weapons, explosives, and other items that pose a danger to others, as well as for financing activities to organize mass riots. Furthermore, it has been stipulated that a person who has committed such a crime shall be exempt from criminal liability if they voluntarily report to the authorities about their training, actively assist in uncovering the committed crime or identifying other individuals who have undergone, conducted, organized, or financed such training, as well as the location where the training took place, provided that their actions do not contain elements of any other crime.

Indeed, the changes in legislation will undoubtedly yield results in practice. However, harmonizing the norms of national regulatory documents would be one of the important steps in combating mass disorders. For example, Article 11 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On crime prevention” stipulates that the prosecutor's office carries out the prevention of offenses, including tax and currency-related violations, money laundering of proceeds from criminal activity, *financing of terrorism and financing the proliferation of weapons of mass destruction*, including identifying and eliminating the causes of these offenses and the conditions facilitating them. [4] However, the law itself does not contain specific provisions for the prevention and suppression of mass disorders.

According to data from the non-governmental organization ACLED (Armed Conflict Location & Event Data Project) and the Bridging Divides Initiative (BDI) at Princeton University, between January 2020 and March 2022, a total of 1,040 incidents of unrest of various scales were recorded in the United States, resulting in at least 26 fatalities. [5]

The foundations of the process of criminalizing mass riots can be determined by identifying the following criminal-legal and criminological characteristics of mass riots: their violent nature; heterogeneity of the individuals involved; extremist orientation and motivation; “mass character” which is expressed in significant quantitative indicators of the riot participants; the potential to become a means of carrying out “color revolutions” as well as the possibility of evolving into a form of political crime.

American federal criminal legislation does not differentiate criminal liability for subjects involved in mass riots based on their functions as organizers, instigators, assistants, or direct participants. A comparative legal analysis of § 231 (Civil Disorders) and § 2101 (Riots) of the U.S. Code, considering the specific features of the material element of mass riots, reveals that in the first case, mass riots themselves are not considered a crime. However, criminal liability exists for actions

that contribute to mass riots and increase their social danger: a) Assisting in training future participants of mass riots to acquire skills in handling weapons, explosive, and incendiary devices; b) Preparing to transport or transporting the specified means and weapons with the intention of their subsequent illegal use in mass riots; c) Actions aimed at obstructing, interfering with, or adversely affecting the work of fire service or law enforcement officers lawfully performing their duties during mass riots. [6]

From this perspective, it is advisable to adapt the provisions of Uzbekistan's criminal legislation regarding responsibility for mass riots accordingly.

High-tech means and weapons of crime are objects of the material world, processes, and methods that are qualitatively distinct at an advanced technological level, used by the subject of the crime to organize mass riots, call for mass riots, incite and involve others in mass riots, or directly participate in such disturbances (information and communication technologies in the form of social networks, messaging apps, and others; mobile and satellite communications; unmanned aerial vehicles; 3D printing technologies and the physical destruction tools created based on them). Therefore, the accurate and precise classification of criminal tools used in mass disorders is of crucial importance.

For effective counteraction to such crimes, it is proposed to develop a “Concept on Mass Disorders”, defining the goals, objectives, principles, main activities, and mechanisms of state policy in the field of prevention of mass disorders, based on proactive (projection-based) approaches and taking into account the use of high-technology means.

The current complex socio-economic and political environment, along with ideological fragmentation, has led to the emergence of tensions and conflicts in society based on economic, ethnic, religious, and political differences. This situation inevitably affects the general state of criminality and specific categories of crime, including mass disorders. Given the instability of the global environment, it cannot

be ruled out that various mass events such as rallies, marches, and demonstrations may arise within the country, some of which could negatively affect public order and security. Therefore, considering the ongoing development of society, it would be prudent to anticipate an increase in the incidence of crimes such as mass disorders in certain regions.

When organizing preventive measures, it is necessary to recognize the significant role of social tensions in their emergence and to coordinate the activities of state and public institutions, organizations, and enterprises in this regard. Creating special legislation aimed at unifying the activities of law enforcement agencies in this area would be a logical step forward.

Based on the above considerations, it should be noted that one of the important tasks facing criminal legislation and practice is the legal consolidation of the content, characteristics, and responsibility for mass riots, the precise definition of forms of mass riots, and the improvement of preventive measures and countermeasures against mass riots, taking into account the threats emerging in cyberspace.

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